

Application of ply-by-ply fatigue analysis methodology in the design of a full-scale tidal turbine blade

Stéphane Paboeuf, Luc Mouton, Joseph Praful Tomy, Mael Arhant, Nicolas Dumergue and Peter Davies

Abstract—Tidal turbine blades are subjected to varying intensities of fatigue loads in their installation environment. In comparison with wind turbines, the flow experienced by tidal turbines is more turbulent in nature. Auxiliary factors such as the presence of waves, and alternating tidal currents contribute to the generation of significant fluctuation in the loads experience by a tidal turbine blade. The high speed of rotation of the turbine ensures that the blades experience a high number of fluctuating cycles (order of 10^7) during its service life. Consequently, the estimation of fatigue life of a tidal turbine blade is a significant concern of the blade designer.

The European research project RealTide aims to tackle advanced monitoring, simulation and control of tidal devices in unsteady, highly turbulent realistic tide environments. With a vision to improve the reliability prediction of tidal turbine blades, velocity characterization has been performed at the commercial site of Ushant, off the western coast of France.

Within this paper, a fatigue analysis methodology is proposed that aims to simulate the fatigue strength of the blade using results from quasi-static strength analysis. Realistic operating conditions are estimated using the site measurement data. Blade Element Momentum Theory (BEMT) is used to transform the realistic velocity data into blade forces. Using composite macro-mechanics, the blade forces are converted into ply-by-ply stresses on the laminate. A formulation, based on laminate failure theories, is proposed to convert the macro-mechanical ply-by-ply stresses into equivalent micro-mechanical stresses on the fibres and the matrix. By means of the S-N curve data for uni-directional fibres, the quasi-static micro-mechanical stresses are used to predict the fatigue life of the blade under the test conditions, and the failure model.

Keywords—Fatigue, Fatigue Testing, Ply-by-ply, Realtide, S-N curve, Tidal turbine blade.

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Stéphane Paboeuf and Luc Mouton are with Environment and Technologies Department of Bureau Veritas Marine & Offshore, 4 rue Duguay-Trouin, 44818 Saint-Herblain, France, (emails: stephane.paboeuf@bureauveritas.com, luc.mouton@bureauveritas.com)

I. INTRODUCTION

THE reliability of offshore structures for the production of energy is a primordial issue for technology developers. The knowledge of the environment is important but the control of the mechanical behaviour is essential for designing reliable systems. The objectives of RealTide European research project [1] are to identify main failure causes of tidal turbines at sea and to provide a step change in the design of key components, namely the blades and power take-off systems, adapting them more accurately to the complex environmental tidal conditions.

This paper deals with the fatigue of composite materials blade used for tidal turbines. The first part consists of an explanation of fatigue failure modes of composites and loads applied on blades. Then, the fatigue assessment methodology, based on a ply-by-ply approach, is detailed. Finally, fatigue coupons test results, full scale blade tests and a finite Element Model are presented.

II. FATIGUE OF COMPOSITE MATERIALS

Fatigue is defined as an accumulation of damage due to stress below the normal static breaking strength, leading to fracture. Two types of fatigue exist: the dynamic fatigue caused by cyclic loads and the static fatigue (creep) due to static loads over a long period of time [2]. For marine application, cyclic loads cause more damage than static loads.

A. Fatigue failure modes

The mechanism of the fatigue process in composite materials is quite different from the fatigue mechanism in metallic materials. Fibre-reinforced composites are heterogeneous and anisotropic due to their complex structure arrangement. But this particularity is an

Joseph Praful Tomy was at Bureau Veritas Marine & Offshore and he is now with Department of Mechanical Engineering, Technical University of Denmark, Nils Koppels Allé, 2800 Kgs. Lyngby, (email: jpto@mek.dtu.dk)

Maël Arhant, Nicolas Dumergue and Peter Davies are with Marine Structures Laboratory, Ifremer Centre Bretagne, 29280 Plouzané, France, (emails: Peter.Davies@ifremer.fr, Nicolas.Dumergue@ifremer.fr, Mael.Archant@ifremer.fr)

advantage for the fatigue because this micro-structural arrangement allows to slow crack propagation.

In metal, cracks appear on the surface and are visible, but the composite cracks are more complex and are an accumulation of several early damages.

Three basic failure modes have been identified leading to three stages in the fatigue failure process [3]:

1. Matrix cracking

2. Ply delamination

3. Fibre breakage

The first mechanism contributing to the failure is the matrix cracking, generally caused by the fibre reinforcements debonding. Then, these micro-cracks initiate delamination and large-scale crack propagation. Finally, the fibres break under overload.

Nevertheless, in case of high stress, fibres may break directly under low number of cycles.

The following figure Fig.1 shows the comparison of the loss of rigidity of the composites and the damage evolution during the cyclic loading.

Fig. 1. Rigidity and damage evolution during cyclic loads

During the cyclic loading, the composite material rigidity slightly decreases due to the internal failure and growth of the damage. This typical process can be divided into three stages:

1. Small drop in stiffness associated with the formation of some damage;
2. Damage increases slightly and rigidity falls gradually; and
3. High stress leads to failure.

The fatigue damage of composite materials can be defined by the loss of rigidity depending on the number of cycles.

B. Cyclic loading

Cyclic loading can be defined by a constant amplitude loading characterized by σ_{min} and σ_{max} , see Fig.2. The stress ratio R (1) is a characteristic loading parameter:

$$R = \frac{\sigma_{min}}{\sigma_{max}} \tag{1}$$

Fig. 2. Cyclic loading

Different values of R (Fig.3) can be identified, corresponding to the structural loading of the computed structure.

Unlike the metallic fatigue, the composite fatigue can occur in compression due to the fibre buckling.

During experimental tests, the increase of temperature generated by load variation can affect the fatigue performance of the specimen. Particular attention is to be paid to that phenomenon in order to limit the heating. In general, test frequencies can be higher for the bending tests than for the tensile.

Fig. 3. Different values of stress ratio R

C. Loading conditions for tidal turbine blades

A globally accepted framework for fatigue analysis of composite materials does not exist at the time of drafting this document. This is the case even for constant amplitude fatigue loadings. Tidal turbine blades are exposed to loads with varying amplitudes and intensities throughout their service life. Moreover, the laminates experience a cyclic stress state that is multi-axial in nature. For these reasons, literature on fatigue loading conditions of tidal turbines is practically non-existent.

The nature of forces experienced by tidal turbines can be thought of as similar to that of wind turbines. The wind turbine industry, is relatively well established with a good amount of literature on the blade forces. Fatigue loading of wind turbine blades is still a novel topic; however, there are certain investigative studies conducted in this aspect. Rubiella et al [4] provide a comprehensive summary about the state of the art in fatigue modelling of composite wind turbine blades. The various fatigue models that could be implemented for basic fatigue considerations are discussed within this paper.

Fatigue load spectrum characterisation for wind turbine blades is also an ongoing research topic. From the work of Westphal and Nijssen [5], it is understood that the use of Wisper and WisperX spectra [6] is predominant in the wind turbine industry, as they were derived from strain measurements on wind turbine blades in operation. Recent European research projects such as OPTIMAT and Upwind have resulted in improved spectra such as the ‘NEW WISPER’ [7] and ‘NewWisper2’ [8].

The evaluation of fatigue loads by analytical methods is more challenging. Caous et al [9] proposed to consider the multiaxial cyclic stress state on a wind turbine blade by computing the stresses along the principal axes. The idea behind using the principal stress approach is to reduce the problem into a biaxial stress state. Thereafter, the biaxial fluctuating load is represented by the ratio between the stresses in the two directions – the mean stress, the stress amplitude, the phase shift, and the aspect ratio of the ellipse representing the stress state.

III. FATIGUE OF ASSESSMENT METHODOLOGY

During the design stage of a tidal turbine, the fatigue strength assessment of the blades is paramount in defining the structural scantling. The fatigue assessment should be indicative about the proposed durability of the structure. However, with the definition of the forces on the blades being a complex task in itself, and with the design of the blade scantlings being an iterative process, the fatigue assessment chiefly borders on a predictive approach. The objective during the design stage is to avoid additional computational effort - the prediction of precise loads is not important, as long as the orders of magnitude of the predicted loads are within an acceptable uncertainty level. In any case, some uncertainties, such as those due to environmental conditions, cannot be avoided regardless of the prediction precision achieved. The uncertainties in the

evaluation procedure are accounted for by using adequate safety factors.

Considering these requirements, and in line with the current industry practice, the fatigue assessment methodology proposed is based on the classical fatigue life models. Based on other works in the literature, the use of fatigue life models, such as S-N curves and Constant Life Diagrams, to estimate fatigue behaviour of composites is limited [10]. A progressive damage model, that serves to predict the crack initiation, propagation, until the final failure of the laminate, is deemed to be computationally intensive for the complex loading environment of a tidal turbine blade. It is therefore proposed to add certain aspects of a phenomenological approach, to include correlation with the actual damage mechanisms of composite materials. The major stage in the fatigue evolution on a composite laminate is the crack propagation stage (Stage 2 in Fig.1). Hence, it would be valuable to enhance the classical fatigue-life models, with the inclusion of effects from this stage of the fatigue evolution. Within the fatigue assessment methodology proposed, such an enhancement is made by evaluating the residual stiffness of the laminate during its service life.

Fig. 4. Global Fatigue Analysis Methodology for Tidal Turbine Blades

A schematic diagram illustrating the proposed global fatigue analysis methodology is shown in Fig.4. The fatigue methodology aims to address the three main complexities associated with the fatigue evaluation problem for a tidal turbine blade – namely, the complexities in the loads, the material and the description of the fatigue phenomenon.

A. Ply-by-ply approach to evaluate fatigue stresses

The characterisation of fatigue behaviour for composite laminates usually requires multi-variant analysis unlike metallic fatigue [11]. The behaviour can be different according to the stress ratio, the laminate configuration (stacking sequence) and the failure mode. A comprehensive fatigue life model that captures all these variations would need to be characterized by S-N curves for multiple stress ratios or by a Constant Life Diagram. Such a characterization would require an intensive experimental campaign. Moreover, as the behaviour is different for each stacking sequence within a turbine blade,

such a characterization is impractical from a design perspective.

In static analysis of composite materials, the globally used method is the ply-by-ply analysis, wherein the anisotropy of the laminate description is considered by using an orthotropic simplification. All the mechanical properties of the composite laminate can be simplified into three orthogonal planes – parallel to the fibre direction (L-direction), perpendicular to the fibre direction (T-direction) and through the thickness of the laminate (N-direction) (see Fig.5). While considering unidirectional plies, the properties in the L-direction are dominated by the fibres, and those in the T-direction and N-direction by the matrix.

Fig. 5. Composite laminate orthogonal axes

A ply-by-ply analysis methodology defines the behaviour of each ply (or layer) within the laminate separately. The individual stresses on each layer depend on the mechanical properties (moduli) of the particular layer, its position in the laminate thickness and the global strain of the laminate. For each ply, the elastic stresses in the L and T directions as well as the shear stress in the L-T plane can be thus obtained. This gives the two-dimensional stress state of the ply, which can subsequently be used to determine its mechanical behaviour. This kind of design philosophy is used for static analysis of composite laminates (for example NR546 BV Rules for Composite Materials [12]), and the idea is to extend such an approach for cases when the laminate is subjected to fluctuating stresses, i.e. for fatigue loading.

B. Fibre and matrix stresses

For any given laminate load (bending moment or axial loads), the stresses on each ply in the stacking sequence can be obtained using composite macro-mechanical tools. Such tools predict the stresses in the L-T plane: σ_1 (axial force along the fibre direction), σ_2 (axial force perpendicular to the fibre direction), and τ_{12} (in-plane shear). Within the evaluation studies performed as part of this report, ComposeIT, a freeware developed by Bureau Veritas [13], is used for this purpose.

Within the global fatigue analysis methodology, it is required to analyse the fatigue effect on the fibre and matrix separately. In particular, this would help to separately analyse phenomena such as matrix cracking and fibre failure. Therefore, for each lamina, the ply-by-ply stresses are further resolved to obtain equivalent fibre and matrix stresses ($\sigma_{f(eq)}$ and $\sigma_{m(eq)}$ respectively) at the ply level.

From the orthotropic simplification, σ_1 can be considered as acting only on the fibres, and σ_2 can be considered as acting only on the matrix. The in-plane shear, τ_{12} , would have an impact on both the fibre and the matrix, and needs to be investigated separately.

The combined effect of in-plane shear and transverse tensile stresses in facilitating matrix cracking is known in the literature, from sources such as [14]. This is also evident from the considerations of various failure theories for composite materials under multi-axial loading, such as the Tsai-Hill, Tsai-Wu and Hashin criteria [15]. These failure criteria are usually characterized by 3D failure envelopes in a σ_1 - σ_2 - τ_{12} coordinate system. As the consideration here is to evaluate the matrix cracking, only the σ_2 - τ_{12} plane is considered.

The elliptical failure envelope is defined as shown in Fig.6. The extremes of the major axes of the ellipse are defined by the failure states when acted upon only by σ_2 . These points correspond to the ultimate tensile and compressive strengths of the ply in the T direction (or direction 2), i.e. S_{2T} and S_{2C} respectively. Similarly, the minor axis can be defined by the ultimate in-plane shear strength, S_{12} . Knowing the four corners of the ellipse, the failure envelope (black solid line) can be defined. In fact, the ‘elliptical’ failure envelope is defined by two different ellipses, corresponding to the left and right halves respectively in the plane.

Fig.6 Equivalent ply level matrix stress for multi-axial loading

Now, it is presumed that, a quarter-ellipse traced in the same quadrant following the equation of the failure envelope ellipse (red dotted line) represents stress states that correspond to the same damage level. Therefore, for any given biaxial stress state (σ_2, τ_{12}) , an equivalent augmented stress in direction 2 can be computed, which accounts for the in-plane shear effect. In the diagram, this is represented as σ_m and this is used as the equivalent stress acting on the matrix at the ply level. Mathematically, this can be computed as:

$$\sigma_{m(eq)} = \sqrt{\sigma_2^2 + (f_2 \tau_{12})^2},$$

$$\text{where } f_2 = \begin{cases} \frac{S_{2T}}{S_{12}} & \text{for right half} \\ \frac{S_{2C}}{S_{12}} & \text{for left half} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

Here the factor k is used to represent the ratio between the ultimate strength in the T direction and the ultimate shear strength. Depending on the quadrant under consideration, the value of S_2 used would change between S_{2C} and S_{2T} , and the value for S_{12} could be positive or negative. Eventually, $\sigma_{m(eq)}$ has an absolute value always greater than σ_2 .

In the fibre-dominated L-direction, the equivalent stress is taken as equal to the stress along direction 1. That is to say, the effects of σ_2 and τ_{12} are ignored for the fibre equivalent stress. Therefore,

$$\sigma_{f(eq)} = \sigma_1 \tag{3}$$

A similar formulation has been used by Hashin and Rotem [16] while considering the fatigue failure of off-axis plies. The actual formulation from any of the failure theories could be used in the derivation of this equivalent matrix stress. The conceptual understanding of the equivalent matrix stress would remain the same. However, this would result in a much more complicated equation for the equivalent matrix stress; and thus, it is assumed that the elliptical failure envelope gives a reasonably accurate prediction.

C. Residual matrix stiffness and augmented fibre stresses

The matrix cracking would cause a reduction in the laminate stiffness, and consequently a change in the slope of the stress-strain curve is observed. The increased strain due to the stiffness reduction can induce an increased stress on the fibres – as the matrix cracking only reduces the matrix stiffness, and the fibre stiffness is assumed to remain intact. As matrix cracking progresses, thus it can be considered to have a progressive increase in the stresses experienced by the fibres, at the ply level.

In order to analytically formulate this hypothesis, it is required to link the extent of matrix cracking to the number of cycles during the fatigue loading. Within the literature, the usual procedure is to describe the stiffness reduction as a function of the average crack density or the crack spacing [17]. While this link is more logical, in order to facilitate the utility within a fatigue analysis, it is required to express the stiffness reduction as a function of the number of cycles. Such a link was established by Ogin et al. [18] with an expression for the rate of change of stiffness (dE/dN):

$$-\frac{1}{E_0} \cdot \frac{dE}{dN} = A \left[\frac{\sigma_{max}^2}{E_0^2 \left(1 - \frac{E}{E_0}\right)} \right]^n \tag{4}$$

Where:

- E_0 = Young's modulus of the uncracked composite
- σ_{max} = Maximum stress in the constant-amplitude fatigue cycle
- E = Stiffness after any given number of cycles (N)
- A, n = Constants determined experimentally

Integration of (4) gives the instantaneous stiffness of the laminate as a function of the number of cycles:

$$E(N) = E_0 \times \left[1 - \left(\frac{A}{k}\right)^k \left(\frac{\sigma_{max}^2}{E_0^2}\right)^{1-k} N^k \right] \tag{5}$$

In the classical S-N curve, the number of cycles to failure is obtained by the intersection of the curve with a horizontal line (parallel to the N-axis) at the maximum cyclic stress (σ_{max}). This equation provides a curvilinear path to follow, at a given σ_{max} based on a phenomenological model. From an S-N curve referential, such a model would predict an earlier fibre failure, by accounting for the gradual accumulation of matrix cracks (see Fig.7).

Fig.7 Illustration of augmented fibre stress due to matrix cracking

D. Evaluation of fatigue life using UD S-N curves

The advantage of having ply level stresses is that the data for fatigue of UD fibres can be used to determine the damage. An evaluation using S-N curves is not direct, as the phenomena of matrix cracking and fibre failure are not completely independent of each other. An expression that links the accumulated matrix cracking to an increase in fibre stresses was presented previously. The subsequent paragraphs provide a framework that implements the use of the fibre and matrix stresses in determining the fatigue life of a laminate with a given stacking sequence.

The procedure for fatigue life evaluation revolves around the classical S-N curve concept. As the S-N curve is a material characteristic, it is different for different laminate stacking sequences. The impracticality of characterising the S-N curve for every laminate in the blade design leads to an approach that is more focused on the micromechanics of the composite laminate. This method proposes to evaluate fibre fatigue and matrix fatigue separately. The procedure for evaluation of fatigue life is enumerated below. Fig.8 illustrates a graphical summary of the procedure.

- i. For any given composite laminate, calculate the ply-by-ply stresses (σ_1, σ_2 and τ_{12}) for the maximum load in a fatigue cycle (F_{max}), using macromechanical laminate analysis tools (for example, ComposeIT [13]).

- ii. Calculate the fibre and matrix stresses. The initial fibre stress (σ_{f0}) as $\sigma_{f0} = \sigma_1$. Stress on matrix (σ_m) is calculated as a combined effect of σ_2 and τ_{12} , using (2).
- iii. Fatigue of matrix: Compare the σ_m with the S-N curve for matrix (tensile or compressive) to compute the number of cycles for matrix damage (N_{fm}).
- iv. Fatigue of fibres: To evaluate the number of cycles to fibre failure (N_{ff}), trace the path of σ_f according to (5), starting from σ_{f0} (see Fig.7).
- v. The design number of cycles to failure can be decided as the minimum of N_{ff} and N_{fm} .

Fig.8 Procedure for fatigue life evaluation using UD S-N curves

The fatigue life behaviour of the matrix is to be obtained from fatigue tests of UD [90] laminates. For these laminates, the fatigue behaviour is dominated by matrix cracking and fibre-matrix debonding. Similarly, the fatigue life behaviour of the fibres is obtained from the fatigue tests of UD [0] laminates. For such laminates, the fatigue loads would lead to eventual failure of the fibres.

It should be noted that the experimental tests for fatigue characterisation of UD [0] laminates are performed with uniaxial loads along the fibre direction. Matrix cracking, leading to a loss in stiffness, is not expected during such tests. However, a realistic loading case would be multi-axial, and would lead to a progressive degradation of the matrix due to cracking. The implementation of augmented fibre stresses in step (iv) of the procedure above is expected to account for this gradual degradation of the laminate strength.

Step (v) of the procedure prescribes to decide the design number of cycles as the minimum of N_{ff} and N_{fm} . In most practical loading cases, it is expected that the matrix cracking would be achieved first, i.e. $N_{fm} < N_{ff}$. Choosing this as the design point would lead to conservative designs, as the crack propagation within a multi-oriented laminate stacking sequence is restricted, as compared to the unidirectional ply. Nevertheless, N_{fm} would give an indication about the expected commencement of progressive fatigue failure (stage 3 in Fig.1) of the laminate. As a further improvement to the methodology, N_{fm} could be not considered as the design point; but a further augmentation of the fibre stresses would need to account for this phase.

The S-N curve data for $R=0.1$ and $R=10$ should provide reasonably conservative estimates of the fatigue behaviour across multiple ranges of stress ratios. Alternatively, techniques that enable to extrapolate the fatigue behaviour from one stress ratio to another can be utilised. Using fatigue life diagrams such as the Goodman diagram to achieve such an extrapolation, would be a valuable addition to the global methodology.

IV. FLUCTUATING FORCES ON A TIDAL TURBINE

The load on the turbine is due to the fluid force acting on it while it rotates in the environment. The rotation of the turbine creates a distribution of fluid force along its length, and this causes a bending moment on the blades along the axial flow direction. If the turbine operates in a steady uniform flow field, with a constant rotational speed, this force distribution remains the same throughout its operation. However, in reality, this force distribution fluctuates due to:

- i. variations in the inflow velocity (tides, waves, turbulence),
- ii. variations in the flow environment (varying density, viscosity, etc.),
- iii. variations in the rotational speed of the turbine.

An accurate analysis of the fatigue loads would need to consider all these types of fluctuations. Table I shows a brief description of these factors [19]. To give an indication about the impact of each of these factors, approximate values of the time period and intensity of these fluctuations are also provided. These are only indicative values, intended to provide an order of magnitude. Time period gives an indication about the duration of each fluctuation, thereby giving an estimate about the expected number of cycles during the service life. The intensity is measured as how much the fluctuation varies from a mean value – it is an approximate ratio of the amplitude of fluctuations (σ_{amp}) to the mean value (σ_{mean}).

The level of detail required in defining the fatigue load spectrum is the choice of the designer, after giving due consideration to the impact of each of these factors. The intensity mentioned in Table I could be used indicatively to understand their relative impacts. Description of

methods to evaluate a combined long-term load distribution is not envisaged within this paper. However, the following paragraphs provide brief descriptions about possible methods that could be employed to account for some of the major fluctuating stress components – namely the stress fluctuations due to tidal flow, turbine rotation and waves.

TABLE I
FORCE FLUCTUATIONS ON A TIDAL TURBINE BLADE

Factor	Time Period	Intensity	How to consider
Tidal flow	12 hours	2 (Reversal of stresses)	Sinusoidal fluctuations during the ebb-flow-ebb cycle
Turbine rotation	0.5 seconds	1/20	Considering operational profile of the turbine
Waves	10 seconds	1/8 (Reversal of stresses)	Requires analysis of irregular wave spectrum at the particular site
Turbulence	0.1 seconds	1/10	Requires CFD analysis
Varying density	Unknown	1/40	Depends on the temperature, salinity and location
Varying viscosity	Unknown	Unknown	Depends on the temperature, salinity and location
Geometry complexity	Unknown	Unknown	Requires CFD analysis to investigate the effect of nacelle, tower, etc.
Geometry complexity	Unknown	Unknown	Requires CFD analysis to investigate the effect of nacelle, tower, etc.

The variation in the inflow velocity could be characterized by sinusoidal fluctuations of the tidal stream velocity. The stress fluctuations would be ranging from the maximum value at the peak ebb tide, to the minimum value at the peak flow tide. As the tide directions invert during one cycle of 12 hours, such fluctuations would be represented by a negative stress ratio – alternating tension and compression. The frequency distribution can be obtained by generating a distribution of the tidal stream velocities at the site, and thereafter converting it into equivalent bending moment spectra and subsequently the stress spectra.

The rotation of the turbine causes high frequency fluctuations of the stresses, in accordance with the rotation speed of the blade. The frequency of these fluctuations corresponds to the number of rotations made by the turbine during its lifetime. Such a frequency distribution can be generated, considering the expected operating profile of the turbine. Typically the blade experiences maximum stress when it is at its highest point and minimum stress when it is at its lowest point. To determine the stress range for each rotation, variation of the axial velocity profile along the depth of the sea could be considered.

The simplest method to consider this variation would be in accordance with a power law [20]. The stress range associated with the fluctuations would be comparatively low, but at high frequency. The stress ratio would be either purely tensile or purely compressive, depending on the ply under consideration.

As the blade is subjected to a spatially varying velocity field, at a constant TSR, for different inflow axial velocities, a dedicated tool, 'StarBlades' [21], based on Blade Element Momentum Theory (BEMT) has been developed within RealTide project. The BEMT computations, are performed for one full rotation of the blade, and for each inflow velocity, a sinusoidally varying root bending moment on the blade is obtained, as can be seen from the figure. A parabolic fit would describe a transfer function between the inflow velocity and the maximum root bending moment. Given a tidal velocity spectrum (which is characteristic of the site), this transfer function can be used to convert it into an equivalent bending moment spectrum. Subsequently, the ply-by-ply approach can be used to transfer it into a stress spectrum.

When the various sources of force fluctuations in a tidal turbine operating environment are accounted for, the result would be in the form a force or bending moment spectra on the entire blade. The next step would be to transform this into equivalent stress spectra, so that the fatigue assessment methodology can be implemented.

Fig.9 Workflow for reference stress calculations using ComposeIT

Fig.9 shows a workflow for this conversion using ComposeIT [13]. ComposeIT tool is based on composite macro-mechanics, and it enables the ply-by-ply stresses on a laminate with a given stacking sequence and applied load to be computed. In the case of a tidal turbine, the laminate loads can be either computed using simple beam theory (see Figure 10) or using a Finite Element Analysis (FEA) model. Once the ply-by-ply stresses for one loading condition are determined, a linear transfer function can be used to convert the bending moment spectrum into a stress spectrum – assuming that the deformation of the blade is linear and elastic. As fatigue damage is accumulated over a large number of cycles, the blade deformation is expected to be linear when subjected to these forces, and the linear elastic assumption is very relevant.

V. EXPERIMENTAL CAMPAIGN

A. Fatigue coupon tests

The present ply-by-ply approach provides a simplified methodology for fatigue analysis, by computing equivalent fibre and matrix stresses. The approach is a shift from the classical method of characterizing the fatigue behaviour of the entire laminate, towards an approach that is more micro-mechanical. As there are multiple failure mechanisms in action during the fatigue of a composite laminate, the validation of this approach is necessary to give an overview about its applicability and limitations.

An interesting database that could be used to test the applicability of this method was obtained from the work

of Kawai et al [22]. These experiments provide a database for fatigue testing of off-axis laminates. From a laminate stacked with 16 unidirectional plies at 0°, samples were cut at different angles – 0°, 10°, 15°, 30°, 45° and 90°.

The validation is performed for multiple stress ratios: R=0.1 for tension-tension fatigue and for R=10 for compression-compression fatigue. These ratios are chosen, since the test data is available for all the orientation angles. It is to be noted that the laminates used for these experiments are unbalanced off-axis plies. Hence, the formation of a matrix crack is likely to lead to a fatal propagation that results in the failure of the entire laminate. Therefore, the failure of the matrix (using the UD 90° S-N curves) is taken as the point at which the laminate is predicted to fail. Only results in tension for R = 0.1 are presented here, see Fig.10.

Fig.10 Experimental and predicted results for fatigue of off axis in tension, R=0.1

For the tensile fatigue S-N curves, the methodology shows very good correlation for all the ply orientation (+10°, +15°, +30°, +45°). The only exception is in the case of +45° for R=0.1, wherein the methodology is more conservative in predicting the fatigue life. The mechanism for failure for all the cases seems to be the tensile failure. A possible reason could be that for the +45° samples, the elliptic approximation of the equivalent matrix stress is quite conservative. For the +45° samples, the ratio $\sigma_y:\tau_{xy}$ is such that it falls almost along the diagonal, and for such a stress state, an elliptical formulation is clearly conservative. Further light on this can be shed from validation with other test data, for [45°] or [±45°] samples.

For the compressive fatigue, Fig.11, the methodology seems to be in good agreement for [+30°] and [+45°] laminates, but it seems to be over-estimating the fatigue life for [+10°] and [+15°] laminates. This might be due to the fact that for the [+10°] and [+15°] laminates, the stress in the L-direction (σ_1) is much higher than that for the other

two laminates. This high compressive stress along the fibre direction can lead to premature micro-buckling of the fibres, which might supersede the matrix cracking fatigue. For [+10°] and [+15°] laminates at R=10, one of the modes of failure is the kink failure – this mode of failure is related to micro-buckling. This mode of failure becomes less significant as the fibre orientation angle increases.

The equivalent matrix stress methodology evaluates compressive fatigue behavior based on the behavior of the [90°] laminates – which fails in out-of-plane shear. This can be extended to plies in [+30°] and [+45°] laminates, but it might be over-estimating the fatigue life of lesser orientation angles. However, in reality, the stacking sequence would be balanced, and such micro-buckling would be prevented. Hence, this methodology is expected to have better agreement for balanced plies subjected to a compressive load.

Fig.11 Experimental and predicted results for fatigue of off axis in compression, R=10

B. Full scale tests of Tidal Turbine Blade

A 5 m length blade has been tested at Ifremer facilities in Brest, France. The tested blade is a new prototype developed by Sabella within RealTide project. A special test frame, see Fig.12, has been designed supporting two hydraulic cylinders allowable to load the blade in 3 points up to failure. A maximal load of 250kN per cylinder is applied through a saddle system as shown in Fig.13 below, based on textile slings. The root of the blade is bolted to a thick plate representing the blade/rotor interface as a clamped connection.

The blade has been highly instrumented by Ifremer and EnerOcean with:

- a set of displacement transducers,
- strain gauges rosettes bonded every 500mm along the top skin,
- 2 acoustic emission transducers,

- 1 optical fibre embedded during blade manufacturing and one placed on the surface after manufacture,
- a novel ultrasonic wave propagation monitoring network with transducers along and inside the blade.

Fig.12 Blade on test frame with instrumentation

Fig.13 Blade load application on test frame with instrumentation

A set of static and cyclic tests have been performed in early 2021 on a first blade and a second blade will be tested during summer 2021. Test results will be presented in other papers.

C. Finite Element Model of Tidal Turbine Blade

A Finite Element Model (FEM), see Fig.14, has been created to simulate the full scale blade tests and for the fatigue assessment under cyclic loads. Laminates are described ply-by-ply by using the ComposeIT-to-FEMAP

interface developed by Bureau Veritas and applied to shell elements as laminate plate.

First simulations have been used for the location of hot spot stresses and indicated the best position of the monitoring system.

Fig.14 Finite Element Model of the full scale tidal turbine blade

Displacements, strains and forces measured during tests will be compared with the calculations for FEM validation.

VI. CONCLUSION

The work performed in collaboration with RealTide project partners allowed a new methodology for the fatigue assessment of composite material tidal turbine blades to be developed. The validation of this method has not yet been completed, however the comparison of experimental data with predicted values seems to indicate that it is a promising approach.

The next step will be to analyse results from fatigue coupon tests performed by Ifremer, to apply the fatigue methodology and to assess the fatigue of the Sabella tidal turbine blade.

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REFERENCES

- [1] RealTide project website, <https://www.realtide.eu/>
- [2] Paul Holden Miller, "Durability of Marine Composites: A study of the effects of fatigue on fiberglass in the marine environment", Marine Technology and Management Group, Civil and Environmental Engineering, University of California, Berkeley, 2000
- [3] Juliette Payan, "Etude du comportement de composites stratifiés sous chargement statique et de fatigue", Ph.D. Thesis, University Aix-Marseille II, 2004
- [4] C. Rubiella, C. A. Hessabi and A. S. Fallah, "State of the art in fatigue modelling of composite wind turbine blades," International Journal of Fatigue, no. 117, pp. 230-245, 2018.
- [5] T. Westphal and R. P. L. Nijssen, "Fatigue life prediction of rotor blade composites: Validation of constant amplitude formulations with variable amplitude experiments," Journal of Physics, no. 555, 2014.

- [6] A. t. Have, "WISPER and WISPERX : final definition of two standardised fatigue loading sequences for wind turbine blades," 1992.
- [7] B. Bulder, J. Perringa and e. al, "NEW WISPER - Creating a New Standard Load Sequence From Modern Wind Turbine Data," 2004.
- [8] R. P. L. Nijssen and T. Westphal, "Upwind Deliverable 3.1.7: Randomising New Wisper - Development and implementation of a method for rainflow equivalent randomisation of variable amplitude sequences -, Upwind".
- [9] D. Caous, C. Bois, J.-C. Wahl, T. Palin-Luc and J. Valette, "Analysis of Multiaxial Cyclic Stress State in a Wind Turbine Blade," in 20th International Conference on Composite Materials, Copenhagen, 2015.
- [10] R. Nijssen, "Fatigue life prediction and strength degradation of wind turbine rotor," Delft University of Technology, 2007.
- [11] C. Bathias, "An engineering point of view about fatigue of polymer matrix composite materials," *International Journal of Fatigue*, vol. 28, pp. 1094-1099, 2006.
- [12] Bureau Veritas, NR546 - Hull in Composite Materials and Plywood, Material Approval, Design Principles, Construction and Survey, DT R02 ed., Paris: Bureau Veritas, 2018.
- [13] Bureau Veritas Marine & Offshore, "Bureau Veritas Software," 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://marine-offshore.bureauveritas.com/software>.
- [14] P. P. Camanho, C. G. Davila, S. T. Pinho, L. Iannucci and P. Robinson, " Prediction of in situ strengths and matrix cracking in composites under transverse tension and in-plane shear," *Composites*, vol. Part A (37), pp. 165-176, 2006.
- [15] R. Talreja, "Assessment of the fundamentals of failure theories for composite," *Composites Science and Technology*, no. 105, pp. 190-201, 2014.
- [16] Z. Hashin and A. Rotem, "A Fatigue Failure Criterion for Fiber Reinforced Materials," *Journal of Composite Materials*, vol. 7, pp. 448-464, 1973.
- [17] K. W. Garrett and J. E. B. , "Multiple transverse fracture in 90° cross-ply laminates of a glass fibre-reinforced polyester," *Journal of Materials Science*, no. 12, pp. 157-168, 1977.
- [18] S. Ogin, P. Smith and P. Beaumont, "Matrix Cracking and Stiffness Reduction during the Fatigue of a (0/90)s GFRP Laminate," *Composites Science and Technology*, no. 22, pp. 23-31, 1985.
- [19] L. Mouton, S. Paboef, J.P. Praful, , D. Caous, J. Valette, "Implementing realistic environmental loads on the fatigue testing of a prototype tidal turbine blade", EWTEC, Plymouth, 2021
- [20] N.-S. Cheng, "Power-law index for velocity profiles in open channel flows," *Advances in Water Resources*, no. 30, pp. 1775-1784, 2007.
- [21] RealTide Project, "D3.1 - Generalised Tide-to-Wire model," RealTide Consortium, 2019.
- [22] M. Kawai and N. Itoh, "A failure-mode based anisomorphic constant life diagram for a unidirectional carbon/epoxy laminate under off-axis fatigue loading at room temperature," *Journal of Composite Materials*, vol. 48, no. 5, pp. 571-592, 2014.